
KNOWING AND UNKNOWING

Chos skyong skyabs མོས་སྤྱོད་སྤྱུག་ལ། (Qiejiangjia 切江加)*

When I was about five, my friends and I played with frogs near a small stream in late spring. The stream had many twists and turns as it flowed eastward between our neighbor's house and my home. By mid-spring, the ice had gone. Fresh grass began covering the ground, new flowers appeared, and animals were waking up from hibernation. Marmots were coming out of their dens and making the sounds marmots make here and there. It seemed like they were greeting each other or competing in the volume and length of their noises. Mother birds anxiously constructed new nests to lay eggs. Frogs joined in this symphony, looking for partners to produce tadpoles. These animals were starting a new year. Even people, in the early morning, were full of energy.

My family severely scolded me when I played with water animals because they are nagas and punish you if you hurt them.

"I need two more," Rin bkra announced as he rolled up his sleeves again and clutched about in the unclean water.

After a bit, he brought up two frogs, screamed, and threw them at me. The legs of one frog extended wide like a bat's wings, spinning in the air like a wheel. I nimbly dodged to the right, avoiding it hitting my face. It passed by my left ear, making a particular sound that repeatedly rang in my ears for a long time. An instant after I turned, the frog struck the edge of a boulder and stuck there for a bit before slowly sliding to the ground. Its belly had split, and its entrails exploded everywhere. Of course, it died in a second. The other frog fell on the grass on its back, waving its legs in the air, seemingly begging for help. Rin bkra stood motionless, his face turning pale as he attempted to come near me.

Later, Rin bkra buried the frog in a hole, covered it with soil, and put a flat stone near the head of a spring. He tried to pull me away, but I couldn't move my legs. We were terrified.

* Chos skyong skyabs. *Knowing and Unknowing. Asian Highlands Perspectives* 63:388-391.

"Don't come back here!" he warned.

I worried about the naga's punishment, especially when I recalled a little girl's story that Grandfather had told me:

A little girl lived with a single mother in a small wooden house near a creek in front of a tree-covered mountain. This was a realm of various animals and birds. Birds constantly gave twitter performances rivaling professional musicians displaying their abilities in a concert hall.

The different animals in the forest lived peacefully. There were many stories about that place, but the main idea was that those animals and birds belonged to a powerful naga. People dared not do anything that would offend the naga.

The daughter went to the nearest spring to fetch water every morning with some milk in her wooden bucket, which she sprinkled into the spring, asking the naga to let her fetch water. Unfortunately, she carelessly set her wooden bucket on a small frog's back legs one day, badly hurting it.

Afterward, she fell seriously ill. Her left calf became very itchy, followed by red blisters that grew bigger and bigger. In time, all her calf was infected. Pus oozed from the blisters and gave off a terrible smell. The infected area moved above the knee and spread to her upper body.

Eventually, she couldn't stand by herself, and her legs became thinner and thinner, resembling chopsticks.

That night, I dreamed someone was calling me. I couldn't turn in the direction of the sound nor move my legs, no matter how hard I tried. After a while, an old man with white hair as long as a horsetail appeared. He had toad skin, an angry face, a frightening voice, wore white clothes, and held a cane in his left hand. When he asked me about the previous day's events at the spring, I was so frightened I couldn't move. My left hand covered my mouth. The old man grabbed my neck and pulled me back to the spring. I was dizzy.

We were in a strange place when I regained consciousness. Rin bkra was also there, tied to an ancient tree, his head hung low and tree branches tightly binding his wrists and ankles. He didn't

look at me. His belly had a big bleeding wound. The place was muddy and smelled awful, almost making me lose consciousness again. The old man led me to the King of Nagas. I tried to explain that I had done nothing with the frogs but couldn't make a sound.

Suddenly I started yelling and running, terrified of being grabbed and beaten. My legs wouldn't move as fast as I wanted. Then I woke up just as someone grabbed me from behind.

I dreamed of frogs a million times after that. I have a strong aversion to all water animals. I vomit, feel dizzy when encountering water animals, and have no appetite for several days. I like winter because there are no water animals.

My situation steadily deteriorated. I slept poorly. My family members almost lost hope that I would become normal. I visited many *bla ma*, tantric practitioners, holy places, and monasteries near my home area, seeking a cure. My family sponsored countless religious rituals, but there were no positive results.

I and some relatives happened to meet a tantric practitioner on a Lha sa street when I was fifteen. Glancing at me, he asked one of my relatives, "Is there something wrong with this boy?"

"Yes! Your Holiness," was the instant reply.

The tantric practitioner sat in the street, took out a wooden bowl, and poured water from a bottle into it. He took a *rkang gling* 'human thigh-bone horn' from his shoulder bag, spat water on me, chanted loudly, shook his head, blew the horn, and said, "A powerful naga has attacked this boy. Has he done something bad to nagas?"

After a relative explained everything, the tantric practitioner advised me to return home quickly and do rituals there. He recommended several rituals and scriptures to chant.

We returned home. Nothing changed despite inviting holy *bla ma*, monks, and tantric practitioners daily to our home and the springhead.

Later, we visited a hospital in the capital city. After many examinations, a doctor declared, "This boy will soon go mad if we don't treat him," and used a lot of medical jargon we didn't

understand.

Still, we were very interested when he said, "When a child has been terribly scared, fear attacks the heart, which cannot return to normal."

Doctors have asked millions of questions in the past seventy-five days. I've already recovered much more than my relatives, or I expected.

TIBETAN TERMS

bla ma བླ་མ།

chos skyong skyabs ཚོས་སྤོང་སྐྱབས།

lha sa ལྷ་ས།

rin bkra རིན་བཀྲ།

rkang gling ཀང་གླིང་།

CHINESE TERM

Qiejiangjia 切江加